

proof of the converse of Pythagoras' theorem through the law of cosines

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Given: 1. triangle abc; 2. $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$

Prove: $\alpha = 90^\circ$

Proof

cosine law for angle α : $c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab\cos\alpha$ (1)

on the other side (according to the problem statement): $c^2 = a^2 + b^2$ (2)

(1) - (2): $c^2 - c^2 = a^2 - a^2 + b^2 - b^2 - 2ab\cos\alpha$

$\Rightarrow \cos\alpha = 0$

$\Rightarrow \alpha = \pm\arccos(0) + 2\pi n$, где n – integer, whole number

$\Rightarrow \alpha = 90^\circ$

the converse of Pythagoras' theorem is proven